

From Televangelism to *Antiqua et Nova*: Navigating the Shifting Sands of Faith in the Age of AI

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Abstract: *The intersection of artificial intelligence (AI) and religion presents an innovative yet complex landscape, demanding careful consideration of its ethical and anthropological implications. The recent joint doctrinal note, Antiqua et Nova, issued by the Dicasteries for the Doctrine of the Faith and for Culture and Education, highlights ethical challenges posed by dependency on AI. This paper explores the changing relationship between faith and technology, tracing its development from early media evangelism, such as televangelism, to the challenges of advanced AI tools. It examines the transition from "religion online" to "online religion" and "digital religion," emphasizing how these stages have influenced practices and discussions. Antiqua et Nova serves as a crucial document not only in terms of religious use of technology but also in addressing anxieties over the diminishment of human knowledge and ethical predicaments from AI integration. The paper situates Antiqua et Nova in the context of technology's influence on religion and questions whether fascination with AI is a beneficial evolution or a harmful shift in the understanding and practice of faith. The document advocates a thoughtful approach, encouraging AI's development and application in ways that respect human dignity, promote justice, and support comprehensive human development..*

Keywords: *Antiqua et Nova, Televangelism, AI, ethics, Digital Religion.*

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The connection between religion and technology has been intensely reciprocal, each significantly shaping the other's diffusion and impact. The digital shift has enabled a more fluid engagement with religious practices. Sacred space has expanded beyond physical places of worship, transitioning to online platforms that assist broader and more dynamic involvement for the faithful. From communication technologies to AI tools, different religious organizations have adapted to the changing patterns of time to cater to their faithful effectively. For example, religious organizations utilize communication tools such as online sermons, social media groups, live streaming, and apps to strengthen their communities. Their goal is to provide followers with a cohesive and unified experience that transcends geographical boundaries (Haden et al., 2020).

In the pretechnological era, cave paintings, encryptions, and folk-art forms were used by religious groups to narrate the philosophy of their religious teachings. These traditional forms of media have a crucial role in promoting religious practices and products and later paved the way for using modern technologies like print, broadcast, and new media (Couldry, 2003; Lövheima & Lynchb, 2011).

Religion is associated with faith, tradition, and rituals. It is a phenomenon where an individual's faith is strengthened by the traditions of their group, with faith being a crucial element that effectively transmits this tradition to others (Devine, 1986). The sociology of religion views it as a unique aspect of human existence, reflecting on the ultimate meaning of life (Luckmann, 1990). Psychologists held different notions of religion. Kirkpatrick explained it as secure attachment, as a child feels towards its parent (Devine, 1986; Granqvist, 2006; Granqvist et al., 2010; Kirkpatrick, 2012; Kirkpatrick & Shaver, 1990); Freud suggested a person develops religious affiliations due to deep emotional conflict and life-threatening weaknesses, and Nietzsche and Marx criticized religion for promoting the value of weakness, arguing that religious dependency on God is a weakness (Reiss, 2000). Despite the varied psycho-social factors, religion significantly influences an individual's mental stages, resulting in diverse experiences of faith.

With the ever-growing phenomenon of digitalization, which has nearly permeated all aspects of life, scholars of different domains have begun to examine fundamental questions considering the influence of digital technology on religion and spirituality, which are old yet adapting to new forms of space and practices (Jetter, 2024). Artificial intelligence (AI), with the rapid advancement of technology, has taken the internet to another stage. With its myriads of options, AI is increasingly automating and augmenting many functions previously performed by human beings. While the advancement of technology is generally viewed as beneficial, the ethical implications of AI's widespread use raise concerns about the broader moral and social consequences of these systems (Tan, 2020). The recent joint doctrinal note, 'Antiqua et Nova', issued by the Dicasteries for the Doctrine of the Faith and for Culture and Education, highlights the potential ethical challenges posed by inundated dependency on AI. This essential document advocates for a balanced approach, encouraging us to consider both the technological advancements AI offers and its significant societal and moral implications. The 'Antiqua et Nova' emphasizes the importance of being cautious about over-relying on AI. However, it also recognizes that technology can enhance, rather than replace, deeply human and spiritual pursuits. While technology cannot replace religious experiences, using it thoughtfully in religious practices can greatly enhance the understanding of religious teachings and practices.

Innovating Faith: Adaptation of Technology for Religious Practices

Technological intervention has touched every sphere of daily life, making it easier to access goods and services. Communication tools are highly visible and impactful representations of technology's influence on religion, profoundly shaping religious experiences, ethical considerations, and access to information. iPhone was called "Jesus Phone". It is an example of how religious imagery and language are used to sell technology. From the printing press to AI tools, traditional and new techniques of communication complement religion. Undeniably, these tools have significantly reshaped how religious information is distributed and how communities relate (Constantin et al., 2024).

Religion in the digital age is an irresistible process- a rapidly evolving landscape with concrete, tangible shifts in how religion is practised, understood, and disseminated. It is changing the understanding of what it means to be spiritual or religious (Bingaman, 2023). For instance, during the pandemic, livestreamed services became a lifeline.

Adapting technology into religion was speculative, with the fear of secularization of the religion. Prominent sociologist Luckman believed that religion would not vanish from society but would shrink in modern society (Brummans et al., 2013; Hoover, 2006; Luckmann, 1990). Technology is a byproduct of human inventiveness to accomplish practical tasks, and it cannot be completed without the intervention of human beings. Hence, it is a human, instrumental, rather than god- like instrument (Campbell, 2005b; Hosseini, 2008).

The philosophy of technology describes technology as ‘enframing,’ ‘saving power,’ and ‘constellations,’ suggesting that it possesses a divine power, bridging the gap between God and humanity. For Socrates, Philosophy was about opening up to the divine realm, a realm of ideas. It is not about bringing God to man, but rather, elevating humans to God with his ideas, creativity, innovations, and intellect. According to the Philosophy of Being, an object remains just an object until human inquiry intervenes with it. Indeed, humans are subject to whatever truth they possess; hence, technology cannot be higher than the capability of human beings themselves (H. Campbell, 2005a).

Church is open to the advancement of science, technology, and all forms of human endeavour as part of human collaboration with God in perfecting the creation. It is considered a God-given skill at work. Technology is created to “imitate the human intelligence that designed it”, often surpassing the skill and speed of what humans can do (Fernandez et al., 2025).

Philosopher Heidegger, one of the most influential thinkers of the twentieth century, considered that technology has been integrated into human use, and human beings’ freedom and determination over

technology is very remote. Since the technological revolution has forced human beings to act according to technology, it destroys the intrinsic nature of human thinking. He held two views on technology: ‘Technology is a means to an end’; and ‘technology is a human activity’(Belk, 2013; Heidegger, 1954; Hosseini, 2008).

“Antiqua et Nova: Note on the Relationship Between Artificial Intelligence and Human Intelligence”, is a doctrinal note co-issued by the Dicastery for the Doctrine of the Faith and the Dicastery for Culture and Education addresses the anthropological and ethical challenges raised by AI from a catholic perspective emphasizing the dignity of the human person, ethical responsibility and future of the society.

The Evolving Interface: From Televangelism to Artificial Intelligence in Religious Practice

The printing press, which was part of the evangelical reformation in the sixteenth century, was used to preach God and established a communication pattern. Press created a standard for the proliferation of information, creating a different sense of community and society. The translation of belief from one medium to another reshaped the human social network and the relationship between humans and the divine (Lundby, 2011). In 1997, the Vatican expressed “media as a divine blessing and gift,” which is seen as the official acceptance of the catholic church to accept technical advancements in its traditions and rituals (Campbell, 2007; Hosseini, 2008).

In the genre of studies of religion and Media, one of the most frequently and substantially touched fields is Televangelism. Televangelism is situating religion in the “secular” realm of the media, where it takes the form of transforming both religion and broadcasting (Hoover, 1997). While Television was still a new invention in the early 1950s, the Roman Catholic church used it as a medium to telecast the religious message delivered by Rev. Fulton J Sheen, a notable Catholic Priest. It was a shift from doctrines to making meaning to daily practices of life. Through the instrumentalist approach to media as a channel for

transmitting religious messages, television became a temporal “sacred space” for interpreting meaning, identities, and social relationships.

Although televangelism was a great method of preaching religion, it was not accepted without criticism. While televangelism was still a new breakthrough in the 1980s, televangelism critics held the opinion that the Christian Gospel could not be communicated authentically through Mass Media as it lost its essence (Hoover, 1997).

In the early 2000s, there was an amplification of seminars on “religion and media”, “religion in the public sphere”, “Digital religion”, “material culture of religion”, and so on. Jeremy Stolow (2005) termed this phenomenon ‘religion as media’ (Morgan, 2013). Media shapes the understanding of religious narratives by acting as both a mediator and through a process known as mediatization. It serves as a platform for constructing religious meaning in various contexts. The relationship between media and religion unfolds in two main ways: through the symbolic production of content and the consumption and interpretation of that content. In this process, the media interprets the meanings for audiences from a layperson’s perspective.

Research on Digital religion can be categorized into four waves: First stage was a descriptive stage, which was focused on documenting the salient features of each religious community online; in stage two, scholars focused on distinctive characteristics of online behaviors of individuals and communities online; on the third stage, research was focused on emerging trend of offline communities using digital platforms and technologies for better outreach to the members and making their presence easily available online; fourth stage of research has focused on compatibility between the online and offline religious communities – their practices and rituals (H. A. Campbell & Vitullo, 2016; Cheong, 2017). Moving on to the fifth stage, the studies focus on the religion’s responsible use of AI and the ethical implications of the use of AI tools for building a true and just community (Ahmed et al., 2024; Singler & Watts, 2024).

One of the approaches that religious users leverage technology is the ‘domestication approach’, where technology is adapted into the social sphere for wider usage for their own purposes. This was the religious groups’ primary style of technological adaptation (H. Campbell, 2005a). In the context of the domestication of technology is “spiritualizing technology” (H. Campbell, 2005b). That is, the intentional process of actively shaping digital platforms and devices to make them suitable for religious purposes guided by spiritual values. For instance, when technology is viewed as a creation of God, it is considered part of God’s divine design. In this perspective, humans act as stewards of that creation. Therefore, engaging with technology is not only permissible but also a mandate.

Two major Theories that run through the study of media and religion are Mediation (1993) and Mediatization (2008). These paradigms discuss the effects of media, illustrating how it influences thoughts, attitudes, and behaviors. Additionally, media can persuade individuals and communities to adapt to its culture for its own sake.

Mediation is a material form of media such as books, images, songs, etc – ‘the material Culture’- as specified by Morgan (2009) that helps in experiencing the divine (Campbell & Evolvi, 2020). It is the expression of experiencing religion through media in the forms of narration, images, sounds, objects, architecture, rituals, and so on. Mediatization is where the media shapes religious institutions and their practices. It has a long-term effect on society as it is a process through which religious beliefs, agency, and symbols are influenced by the workings of various media (Hjarvard, 2011; Lövheim & Hjarvard, 2019; Morgan, 2011).

Mediatization emphasizes the media’s role in shaping societal and cultural processes. In the context of religious mediatization, media have become key creators and distributors of religious imagery across communities (Hjarvard, 2008; Lövheim & Hjarvard, 2019). Mediatization not only influences the mediation of religion in society but also affects religion’s core elements and principles. It is feared that the moral values

of religion can get tarnished due to the origin of banal religion (Lövheima & Lynchb, 2011).

AI is a game-changer for mediatization, pushing it into a new, more intensive phase often referred to as ‘deep mediatization’ (Hepp, 2019). AI tools such as ChatGPT and Deepfake can curate religious narratives and monitor sentiment towards selected religious issues, which may be disturbing, and further circulate them on social media, influencing the behavioural patterns of the wider circle. The manipulative nature of the AI is not identifiable to the layman, and such content is taken for its face value without questioning its authenticity (Leśniczak, 2024).

Influence of the Digital Age on Religion

The first religion-oriented online activity was ‘create your Own religion’, a bulletin Board system developed by two students at Chicago University in the 1980s, which was part of a virtual forum called “CommuniTree” (Campbell, 2010; Campbell & Lövheim, 2011). The initial online community program was referred to as “virtual communities.” Gradually, other religious groups began to surface on Usenet. *www.ecunet.org*, is the first ecumenical network online. In 1992, the first Church of Cyberspace was established by American Presbyterians (Campbell, 2007; Campbell & Vitullo, 2016). In the mid-1990s, studies were focusing on how the Internet was being utilized for spiritual activities. Until then, Print, Broadcast, and other mediums were in use to disseminate religious information by major religious groups (Campbell, 2005b; Krüger, 2005).

Research on religion and the internet emerged in the 1990s, starting with documenting religious engagement online and its implications for religious beliefs and practices. The research focused on several key areas: the exploration of religious rituals and practices online, the influence of the internet on the definitions and understanding of religion, the relationship between online and offline forms of religion, and the examination of various religious communities, identities, and authorities in relation to the internet (Campbell, 2013, 2017a).

Computer-mediated communication (CMC) gained the attention of the internet as a social network platform for maintaining relationships, playing games, and receiving emotional support. Gradually, the internet was considered a place not only a sphere of connection but also an ‘otherworldly space’ an online “sacramental space’ that allowed people to engage in spiritual pursuits (Campbell, 2004).

A study by Pew Internet and the American Life Project (2001) disclosed that 25% of U S internet users have benefited from spiritual and religious content through the internet, and by the year 2004, it had increased to 64% (Krüger, 2005). The internet brought the freedom for individuals to seek religious knowledge autonomously rather than depending on traditional religious figures. In addition to supporting individualized religious practices, it also raised concerns about the secularism model of religious engagement (Armfield & Holbert, 2003; Campbell, 2013; Krüger, 2005).

A breakthrough in the scholarly studies of religion and the internet came in after the International Conference on Religion and Computer-Mediated Communication (CMC) held in Copenhagen in 2001. Being in the initial stages of religious activity going online, the major queries raised were “What does the internet do to religions? How do religious experiences get mediated online? What are the ways religious groups and individuals adapt to the virtual culture? (Campbell & Vitullo, 2016).

After the initial fascination with digital technology and the technological evolution leading to AI, the Vatican cautioned about the limitations of the technology. While AI offers a wide range of functionalities, it lacks the depth of physical experience and the emotional sensitivity inherent in human beings, which are crucial for recognizing truth and goodness. No machine that operates only with data can compare to the wisdom and new insights gained from personal experiences such as illness, the warmth of love, acts of reconciliation, the beauty of a sunset, and many other moments in our lives (Fernandez et al., 2025).

Digital Platforms and Religious Organisations

The Internet is known as the ‘network of networks’; it encompasses various technologies designed for different purposes and practices, each contributing to its unique culture (Campbell & Delashmutt, 2014). Religious groups shape and frame the technology in a way that is socially and religiously acceptable and relevant. Heidi Campbell termed it the “Religious Spiritual Shaping of Technology.” In this sense, an online platform can be an imaginary space codified to reflect the religious vision of its leaders, or the leaders may use it as a space for control, engagement, and building their communities (Campbell, 2010; Campbell & Delashmutt, 2014; Cheong et al., 2009b). With the advancement of AI and robotic technologies, the experience of religion has moved from a controlled experience provided by religious groups to the embodiment of spiritual experience in body and soul through virtual or augmented reality (Farman et al., 2024).

In the late 2000s, studies on religious communication and technology were discussed under the umbrella term ‘Digital Religion Studies’. In the 1990s and early 2000s, digital religion studies were known as ‘Cyber-religion,’ where the focus of study was limited to religious groups’ use of the internet (H. A. Campbell & Vitullo, 2016).

The contribution of Helland towards identifying varied perceptions of the Internet and religion is considerable. He coined the terms and presented the distinction between Online religion and Religion online. This distinction was the trajectory for finding new nuances and theoretical approaches for studying religious presence online (Campbell & Vitullo, 2016; Helland, 2005).

Religion Online is an organized effort of religious organizations to communicate with many by providing information about the services related to particular religious groups or traditions (Brummans et al., 2013; Cheong et al., 2009; Hackett, 2006; Lövheim & Campbell, 2017). Major religions in the world- Christianity, Islam, Hinduism, Judaism, Buddhism, etc. come under organized or institutional religions. The rise of “Religion-Online” has created new “sacred spaces” for faith in the

information age. Religion online offers multiple options in a competitive market, prompting major religious organizations to engage in marketing strategies to ensure their growth and survival. For example, in 1996, Tibetan monks performed a special ceremony in New York, bestowing a Buddhist blessing over cyberspace using a tantric ritual, thereby demonstrating the internet as a sacred space (Campbell, 2005a).

“Online religion” is a concept that encompasses various ways religious practices manifest in the digital sphere, such as streaming of religious services, providing religious texts, and using social media to share religious messages. It goes beyond the use of the internet as a tool but creates new forms of religious expression and community within the digital realm (Hirschkind, 2012; Przywara et al., 2021). On the other hand, the members of the organization use social media on their own terms to promote organizational unity (Church & Feller, 2020).

The expansion of online social networks in the mid-1990s, and the gradual launch and growth of Facebook in 2004, paved the way for its users to create a simple digital extension of one’s personal circle of friendship and relationships (Lundby, 2011; Verschoor-Kirss, 2012). Social media is social networking online sites that allow individuals to interact with each other, share feelings, thoughts, observations, experiences, and so on with others, and allow other individuals to post their share of life experiences (Demiroğlu & Taş, 2021). Religious groups have adopted social network technology in two ways- creating their own space in the social network sites that are religious-centric and exclusive, and secondly, making use of the functions of social networks, such as Facebook, YouTube, podcast, etc, for their own advantage (Battista, 2024; Lundby, 2011; Verschoor-Kirss, 2012).

Religion Online/ Online Religion is not all about the application of technology; rather, it is about generating new forms of religious expression online. It is a top-down model of imparting religion, where online communities virtually provide reflections and guidance on religion for its offline members.

Religiosity in young people acts as a protective factor against unwanted behaviours and functions as an agent of subjective well-being. For ‘Digital Natives’, devices with an internet connection become a tool for spiritual connectivity. They consider social media posts and shares as expressions of feelings and try to associate with them as a ‘community of the heart that evokes a memory, feeling, imagination, and thinking’ to share a human spirit. Digital natives who grow up in a technology-saturated world experience spirituality in more flexible and personal ways, with the intersection of online religion (H. A. Campbell & Bellar, 2022).

Antiqua et Nova: Bridging Tradition and Transformation

While technological diffusion is making unprecedented headway and impacting every sphere of life, the catholic church cautions against the uncritical adoption of technological progress, which can potentially tamper with fundamental human values. The recent doctrinal note co-issued by the Dicastery for the Doctrine of the Faith and the Dicastery for Culture and Education addresses the obscure anthropological and ethical challenges raised by the proliferation of AI tools.

Human intelligence is not predominantly about completing and performing tasks but about understanding and actively participating with reality in different dimensions and bringing new insights. In *Antique et nova*, Pope Francis brings home the message that the use of the word intelligent in “AI” can be misleading and overlooking the most precious faculty of the human person. He observes that ‘AI should not be seen as an *artificial form* of human intelligence but as a product of it’ (Fernandez et al., 2025).

Technological products reflect the worldview of their developers, owners, users, and regulators. They have the power to shape our world and engage our conscience at the level of values. While machines make technical choices based on the inputs provided or statistical inferences, human beings possess the ability to choose based on their values and emotions. By exercising prudence, artificial intelligence can be utilized to benefit humanity while avoiding applications that could harm human

dignity or the environment. Therefore, the responsible use of technology is viewed as being more value-based rather than merely results-oriented.

AI lacks the depth of physical presence, relational understanding, and the openness of the human heart to truth and goodness. While its capabilities may appear limitless, they cannot match humans' ability to comprehend reality. Therefore, AI should be used as a tool to enhance human intelligence rather than replace the richness of human thought and understanding.

The catastrophic pandemic outbreak in 2020 forced society to let go of traditional ways of living and embrace more convenient methods with the help of technology. As a result, conventional worship practices transitioned to a digital format, similar to the rapid spread of printed material following the invention of the printing press. The virtual world, which had not gained wider popularity until then, became a real world, even for religious worship. Entering these spaces requires not only a leap of faith but also adequate knowledge of technology (Parish, 2020). The Holy Week and Easter Liturgy broadcast by Vatican media in 2020 had millions of viewers around the world (Baker et al., 2020; Church & Feller, 2020). Similarly, during the pandemic, various religions worldwide used technological advantages to provide spiritual care for the vulnerable, the economically disadvantaged, and the sick (Baker et al., 2020a; Gunderson & Cutts, 2021; Parish, 2020).

Digital religion was not a welcome phenomenon without controversy. The studies conducted held the opinion that the internet has the capacity to either build religious solidarity or it may potentially destroy traditional religiosity (Campbell & Vitullo, 2016; Lövheim & Campbell, 2017b). Another perspective asserts that religious groups remaining outside the internet revolution will become isolated, similar to some Puritan communities in the 18th and 19th centuries, who attempted to stop the flow of time in order to preserve their traditions (Campbell, 2004). Therefore, integrating technological advancements into religious practices is not entirely negative; instead, it is essential to stay current

with modern trends and the needs of the generation. Ultimately, it is a byproduct of human intelligence that should be utilized effectively.

Conclusion

The Church acknowledges AI as a powerful tool that can either enhance prosperity or pose serious threats if misused. The document advocates for a thoughtful approach, encouraging the development and application of AI in ways that respect human dignity, promote justice, and support comprehensive human development. It also warns against the risks of reducing human intelligence to mere functionality and emphasizes the importance of maintaining a human-centred approach to technology.

Technostructuralism, a theory that explores the complex relationship between technology and social structures, argues that technology, by its very nature, is neither inherently good, bad, nor neutral. The impact of technology is not predetermined; it can be evaluated based on the social structure, institutions, or established methods of society. Hence, it can be assumed that Information Communication Technologies (ICTs) and Information Technologies (ITs), do not have any direct impact on religion. The divergence or convergence of messages depends upon the way religion approaches and interprets the media (Saeidabadi, 2008).

Neil Postman expressed his views on the perception that technological tools play a crucial role in the exchange of ideas and messages within a culture. He argued that as a social system transitions through stages of “technocracy” and “technopoly”—where culture surrenders to technology—technology begins to dictate the meanings that are produced. This raises concerns that the prominence of technology might ultimately overshadow or even replace God (Heidegger, 1954; Hosseini, 2008).

The Catholic Church has a long history of engaging with and sometimes shaping the development of technology and science, and its approach to AI is no different. Technology, including AI, is a gift from God and can be used to improve human life, but it must be developed

and used in a way that respects human dignity and promotes the common good. There are ways the Catholic Church can beneficially integrate AI into its systems while adhering to its core values.

Paolo Benanti (2024) identifies three levels of AI integration in pastoral care: augmented pastoral care, where AI is used as an auxiliary tool; hybrid pastoral care, which is the combination of AI with personal accompaniment; and AI-enhanced spiritual direction, which uses AI to deepen spiritual reflection (Jimmy, 2025). There are several ways in which AI can benefit religious institutions. For instance, AI tools can enhance administrative and operational efficiency, helping to reduce the administrative burden on priests and staff. These tools can also provide personalized content tailored for learning catechism, studying the Bible, or engaging in youth programs.

Additionally, spiritual topics rank among the most frequently discussed and researched subjects online. AI can serve as a powerful resource for theological research, quickly suggesting scripture passages, historical contexts, and theological reflections for sermons. Furthermore, translation tools can facilitate the dissemination of church teachings.

Using AI in pastoral and spiritual guidance is a sensitive area. *Antiqua et Nova* clearly emphasizes the ethical consideration of never replacing human connection, empathy, or the sacrament. However, AI can be utilized to support and enhance these services.

AI-powered apps and chatbots can help people deepen their faith and maintain mental and spiritual well-being through daily prayers, meditation, or reflection enhanced by audiovisual content.

As technology plays a larger role, loneliness is now an accepted part of modern life. It is a challenge for the religious organizations to strike a balance between the benefits of technology and avoid or limit those factors that are detrimental (Belk, 2013; Bobkowski, 2009; Lau & Yuen, 2013). Research on AI and religion emphasizes that AI should be seen as a spiritual amplifier, reinforcing rather than replacing

the relational dimensions of religion (Apul & Lektawan, 2024; Jimmy, 2025).

New media and computer culture significantly affect users, particularly in relation to discussions within religious online communities. New media gives users the power to control, deconstruct, or better understand the underlying reality it presents. The user has the power to critique reality and, if wished, can create an alternative reality of the world, which contrasts with traditional media where the user can only accept reality (Campbell, 2004, 2007). Pope Benedict XVI's message on the changing nature of religion online was: "Worship God, not technology".

The new media's interactive nature can empower people to manipulate structures and meanings (Campbell, 2004, 2005a). All scientific and technological achievements are ultimately gifts from God; nonetheless, it could also deter a true encounter with reality and eventually lead people to deep and 'melancholic dissatisfaction' with interpersonal relationships or a toxic sense of isolation. The integration of AI in religious practices provides broader access to spiritual content and improved engagement with the younger generation (Joseph & Olalekan, 2024). However, authenticity and ethical considerations cannot be overlooked in this information-overloaded era.

Tracing the trajectory of the church's engagement with technology, it is found that the church was quick to adapt to technological changes. Although technology fosters the dissemination of religious experiences, the doctrinal note from the Catholic church in times of inundated generations of AI tools stands as a reminder to use technology as a machine, a by-product of human intelligence, rather than giving in to the 'Technocratic paradigm,' a terminology used by Pope Francis, which perceives that "all world's problems as solvable through technological means alone, ... as if reality, goodness and truth automatically flow from technological and economic power as such" (pg9). By exercising prudence, AI can be used to benefit humanity while avoiding applications that could damage human dignity or harm the environment. The

responsible usage of technology is considered more value-based than mere result-oriented.

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